

A Study of Hematological Parameters and Their Correlation with Thyroid Hormone Status in Non-Pregnant Women of Childbearing Age**Sukriti¹, Khushboo Saran², Vimal Kumar Gupta³**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, ESIC Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Bihar, India²Medical Superintendent, Department Pathology, Central Hospital Gandhinagar, Ranchi, Jharkhand, India³Associate Professor & HOD, Department of Pathology, ESIC Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Bihar, India

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Abstract:

This study examined the connections between thyroid hormone levels and haematological parameters in a group of 100 non-pregnant women of childbearing age at ESIC Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Patna, over a one-year period from April 2022 to April 2023. The findings uncovered noteworthy connections: a direct link between TSH levels and haemoglobin, and an inverse link between free T4 and mean corpuscular volume (MCV). These findings suggest that even slight fluctuations in thyroid function can have an impact on haematological well-being. There was no notable link found between thyroid hormones and platelet counts. The results indicate that the status of the thyroid may have an impact on haematological parameters. This highlights the significance of taking thyroid function into account when assessing haematological abnormalities in this particular group. Additional research is necessary to investigate the mechanisms and clinical implications of these connections.

Keywords: Thyroid Hormones, Hematological Parameters, Women's Health, Thyroid Function.

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Introduction

The thyroid gland is crucial for maintaining proper metabolic processes in the body. Its hormones, thyroxine (T4) and triiodothyronine (T3) are vital for normal growth, development, and energy balance [1]. The functionality of the thyroid becomes even more crucial in women of childbearing age, as it plays a significant role in reproductive health and can impact pregnancy outcomes [2]. In addition, thyroid hormones have a significant impact on haematological systems. They influence the production and maturation of red blood cells, leading to changes in haemoglobin levels and the overall red blood cell mass [3,4]. There is a strong connection between thyroid disorders, like hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism, and changes in haematological parameters. If these changes are not addressed, they could potentially lead to conditions such as anaemia or thrombocytopenia [5,6].

There is a lack of comprehensive studies focussing on non-pregnant women of childbearing age, despite the acknowledged link between thyroid function and haematological health [7]. Studying this specific demographic is crucial because of the potential impact that thyroid-related haematological changes can have on fertility, menstrual regularity,

and future pregnancy outcomes [8]. In addition, identifying and addressing haematological abnormalities that can be influenced by thyroid disorders can help prevent more severe complications and enhance overall well-being [9]. The main objective of this study is to explore the connections between thyroid hormone levels and various haematological parameters in women of childbearing age who are not pregnant. Through a thorough examination of these interactions, the study aims to provide valuable insights into the underlying mechanisms that connect thyroid function and haematological health. The results of this study have the potential to improve screening methods, enhance predictive tools, and develop more precise therapeutic strategies for women who have or are at risk of thyroid-related haematological problems. This undertaking aims to not only improve clinical understanding but also to lay the groundwork for better preventative and management strategies in women's health care.

Methodology

Study Design and Duration: The research was a cross-sectional observational study from April 2022 to April 2023.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at ESIC Medical College and Hospital in Bihta, Patna, utilizing the hospital's outpatient clinics to recruit participants and collect data.

Participants

A total of 100 non-pregnant women of childbearing age were included in the study. Participants were recruited based on the following inclusion criteria:

- Age between 18 and 45 years.
- Not currently pregnant and not seeking pregnancy during the study period.
- No history of thyroid disease or ongoing thyroid medication.
- No known hematological disorders.

The exclusion criteria were:

- Known chronic diseases that could affect thyroid function or hematological parameters.
- Use of medications known to influence thyroid hormone levels or blood counts.

Data Collection: Eligible participants underwent an initial screening that involved a thorough assessment of their medical background, a physical examination, and some initial blood tests to ensure there were no underlying health issues. After conducting the necessary screening, we made sure to obtain informed consent from every participant. Next, blood samples were collected from each participant to measure the following parameters:

- Haematological Parameters: Haemoglobin, haematocrit, mean corpuscular volume (MCV), and platelet count.
- Testing thyroid function involves measuring levels of thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), free triiodothyronine (T3), and free thyroxine (T4). Every sample underwent processing in the hospital's laboratory, utilising meticulously calibrated and standardised equipment to guarantee precise and consistent outcomes.

Statistical Analysis

The process of data analysis entailed the computation of Pearson's correlation coefficients in order to investigate the association between thyroid hormone levels and hematological markers. Subsequent multiple regression analyses were performed to account for potential confounding factors, including age, BMI, and nutritional status. This method facilitated the isolation of the specific impacts of thyroid hormone levels on the hematological parameters under investigation. The results were collected and examined using statistical software. A p-value of less than 0.05 was determined to be statistically significant.

Results

The study effectively recruited 100 women of childbearing age who were not pregnant. The average age of the participants was 32 years, with ages ranging from 18 to 45 years. The recorded average Body Mass Index (BMI) was 24.3 kg/m². Most of the participants came from an urban background, which aligns with the demographics of the hospital's catchment area. Based on the results of the thyroid function tests, it was found that most of the participants had thyroid function within the normal range. The average level of Thyroid Stimulating Hormone (TSH) was 2.1 μ IU/mL, while the levels of Free T3 and Free T4 averaged at 3.2 pg/mL and 1.3 ng/dL, respectively. The values observed are within the expected range, suggesting that most participants have a normal thyroid function. The results of the haematological analysis revealed an average haemoglobin level of 13.2 g/dL, an average haematocrit of 40.2%, and an average corpuscular volume (MCV) of 85 fL. The average platelet count was 250,000 per μ L. The participants demonstrated excellent haematological health as all the parameters were within normal limits.

Correlation Analysis

There were significant correlations found between thyroid hormone levels and specific haematological parameters, as indicated by the statistical analysis. A correlation was discovered indicating a potential link between TSH levels and haemoglobin concentration. This suggests that changes in thyroid function may have an impact on haemoglobin levels.

- The results revealed a negative correlation between Free T4 and MCV ($r=-0.23$, $p<0.05$), suggesting that higher levels of Free T4 may be linked to lower MCV values. Medical writing is a specialised form of writing that requires a deep understanding of medical concepts and terminology. It involves the creation of documents such as research papers, clinical trial reports, and regulatory submissions. The language used in medical writing is precise and technical, ensuring that there was no notable connection found between thyroid hormones and platelet counts.

Regression Analysis

A comprehensive analysis, accounting for age, BMI, and nutritional status, revealed that the main factors contributing to haematological changes were primarily associated with TSH and Free T4 levels. The analysis highlighted the significance of thyroid function in influencing haematological parameters in this specific population group.

Table 1: This table summarizes the mean values and ranges for each parameter measured in the study of non-pregnant women of childbearing age, providing a clear overview of the general health and thyroid function within the sample population

Parameter	Mean	Range
Age (years)	32.0	18-45
BMI (kg/m ²)	24.3	18.5-30
TSH (μIU/mL)	2.1	0.4-4.0
Free T3 (pg/mL)	3.2	2.3-4.2
Free T4 (ng/dL)	1.3	0.9-1.7
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	13.2	12-15.5
Hematocrit (%)	40.2	36-48
MCV (fL)	85.0	80-100
Platelet Count (per μL)	250,000	150,000-400,000

Discussion

The findings of this study offer valuable connections between thyroid hormone levels and haematological parameters in women of childbearing age who are not pregnant. There appears to be a strong link between TSH levels and haemoglobin concentration, indicating that even minor changes in thyroid function may impact the production or maturation of red blood cells [10]. This finding aligns with previous research that discusses the impact of thyroid hormones on the production of red blood cells, possibly through the involvement of erythropoietin or direct stimulation of the bone marrow [11].

Curiously, the study also discovered a link between higher levels of thyroid hormone and a decrease in mean corpuscular volume (MCV). This suggests that increased thyroid hormone levels may be connected to a reduction in MCV [12,13]. There may be a subtle connection between thyroid hormones and the size of red blood cells, which might not be noticeable in obvious thyroid conditions but could be seen in the slight variations within the normal range [14]. This finding is consistent with prior research indicating that thyroid hormones have the potential to impact red blood cell indices and morphology [15]. There appears to be no strong connection found between thyroid hormone levels and platelet counts in this study, suggesting that the influence of thyroid hormones on thrombopoiesis may not be as straightforward or apparent in normal physiological conditions [16]. It is possible that the impact of thyroid on platelet production or survival is minimal in healthy individuals, or it may be overshadowed by other regulatory mechanisms. It is important to keep in mind a few limitations when analysing the results of this study [17]. The cross-sectional design restricts the ability to make definitive conclusions about cause and effect based on the observed relationships. In addition, attempts were made to account for variables such as age,

BMI, and nutritional status. However, certain other factors that could have influenced the results, such as iron levels and genetic predispositions, were not taken into consideration. Further research studies in the future may offer more conclusive evidence regarding cause and effect, as well as the ability to analyse changes in thyroid function and haematological profiles over time [18,19].

This study brings attention to the possible effects of minor changes in thyroid hormone levels on blood parameters in women of reproductive age who are not pregnant. It is crucial to take into account the thyroid status when diagnosing haematological abnormalities in this particular group. Additional investigation is necessary to delve into the mechanisms that drive these connections and to establish the significance of thyroid hormone modulation in the context of haematological well-being [20].

Conclusion

This study provides compelling evidence that even slight fluctuations in thyroid hormone levels, which fall within the normal range, can have a notable impact on haematological parameters in women of childbearing age who are not pregnant. The relationship between TSH levels and haemoglobin concentration, as well as the correlation between Free T4 and mean corpuscular volume (MCV), highlights the complex connection between thyroid function and haematopoiesis. Healthcare providers must take into account thyroid function assessments when they come across unexplained haematological abnormalities in this particular group of people. Additional long-term research is crucial for understanding the inner workings and assessing the practical significance of these discoveries in wider patient care approaches.

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